

MICROCHEMICAL INVESTIGATIONS ON SPOTTED MUSCOVITE MICA.

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The chemical nature of some black spots often found in the muscovite mica of Indian origin has been investigated and from their micro-analytical study it has been proved that they consist of crystallised magnetite imbedded between the mica sheets.

It has been observed that some pieces of the muscovite mica from Nellore (India) contain some minerals imbedded between thin sheets of mica which appear like tiny specks scattered all over the surface. The exact nature of these spots were not known probably due to analytical difficulty resulting from their fineness as well as for their inseparable nature from the main body, as can be judged from the attached photographs and microphotographs. These spots have been investigated in the present paper with the help of a micro method described in an earlier communication.

A qualitative micro analysis of the spotted and the colourless portions of the same piece of mica indicates a difference in their iron contents only and absence of elements like titanium, manganese, etc. This seems to suggest that they might consist of haematite or magnetite particles and obviously the latter as both the ferrous and ferric iron are present in them.

This assumption has further been supported by the paramagnetic nature of these spotted parts when compared with the colourless portions and also from the ferrous/ferric ratio as determined by the micro-volumetric method. They are, therefore, regarded as fine particles of crystallised magnetite imbedded between the mica films.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pieces of mica representing only the stained parts and free as far as possible from the colourless portions were dissolved in a mixture of hydrofluoric and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 c.c. : 5 c.c.) and analysed for ferrous and ferric iron by the micro volumetric method described in the previous paper (p. 375).

In the titrations for iron, indicator correction was applied when the mica spots were analysed. Ceric sulphate solution (0.009880*N* in dilute sulphuric acid) and *N*/150 titanous chloride (in 2*N* hydrochloric acid) solution were used. The solution required for the titration was of the order of 10⁻¹ c.c. The following results were obtained :—

Ferrous iron (mg.) (ceric sulphate)	...	0.0108	0.0673	0.0651	0.0670	0.1308
Total iron (mg.) (titanous chloride)	...	0.0327	0.2010	0.2010	0.2010	0.3912

The above data show the ratio between ferrous and total iron present in the spots to be about 1:3, a fact which definitely proves the mineral crystallised between the thin films of the mica to be composed of magnetite.

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